

ORION Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

CHECK OUT THE BEARHILL MOUNTAINS CLUB

Pledge of Excellence
American Museum of Science and History

Trifid Nebula, M20
in Sagittarius
Emission, reflection and dark nebulae;
open cluster;
dist=1260(70) pc

Dr. Ted Barnes
Timke-Allen Observatory
8 June 2024, 1:42-2:12 am EDT
180mm ORION Mak-Novt telescope
ZWO ASI294MC-C camera
20948/1000

AMERICAN MUSEUM OF SCIENCE AND HISTORY
PLEDGE OF EXCELLENCE
K-25

Our traveling ORION Astronomical Society Exhibit, newly installed at the AMSE in Oak Ridge on 5 Aug 2025, after two months display at the Oak Ridge Public Library. Installation team Ted Barnes, Juan Carbajo, Rob Fowler, Don Spong and Robert Varner. "And He Built a Crooked House." – R. Heinlein

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Page Three Astronomy

This is like dinosaurs having their picture taken with an asteroid.

Funny Science Fiction

A Facebook Group.

The **ORION Astronomical Society** is a science and astronomy group founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and astronomical activities in East Tennessee. We hold monthly public meetings at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus, and are active at Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO), hosting public events, sharing knowledge of the skies, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, IT experts, artists, students, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20, and student discounts are available. There is no charge for our newsletters and publications, or for participation in most ORION activities.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

VP and Program Chair: David Fields

Social Chair: Noah Frere

Secretary: Rob Fowler

Treasurer: Bob Edwards

Editor: Ted Barnes

Astrotechnologist: Rob Scott

Videographer: Rob Fowler

Obed Site Outreach: Joshua Gray.

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly ORION meeting, chosen to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

From March 2025 we will be working towards issuing a somewhat shorter version of the Trapezium, which will still include important information regarding the monthly ORION presentation, as well as dates and other information regarding Public Stargazes and other notable events relating to ORION and TAO.

Regarding the contents of this revised Trapezium, we have already concluded that some components, such as a separate Astrophotography section, are so important for a publication on amateur astronomy that one really cannot justify excluding them.

Messages from ORION

August is beginning to provide us with better weather for observing following a very cloudy, wet first part of the summer. I recently did some reading about the history of telescopes, which form much of the center of attention of our hobby. The credit for the first telescope goes to the Dutch eyeglass maker Hans Lippershey, who in 1608 aligned a concave eyepiece lens with a convex objective lens; there is a story that he came up with the idea after seeing two children in his shop playing with several lenses that they found made a distant weather vane appear close. His initial refractor magnified objects by a factor of three. After applying for a patent, his government gave him a substantial fee to make copies. Many of the early telescopes were used for surveying and spying on enemy armies. His design was then picked up by Galileo Galilei in 1609 who made some improvements, getting up to a magnification of about 20. After presenting his device to the Venetian Senate, they gave him a lifetime appointment as a lecturer at the University of Padua and doubled his salary. Thanks then to Hans (and the children) and Galileo for getting all of this started.

Congratulations to the occultation team for several recent successful occultation measurements. See further details in articles in this issue.

In August the new moon is August 22, with August 23 – 24 being a good dark sky weekend. The full moon (known as the Sturgeon moon) is August 9. There will not be much opportunity in the evening for planets, except for Saturn which is starting to be visible around 10pm. In the morning Jupiter and Venus are visible and will have a conjunction this month. Recently, as I was driving to the airport around 5am in the morning, I could easily see Jupiter and Venus.

The Perseids meteor shower this year peaks at August 12 – 13. The Perseids is the largest meteor shower of the year; unfortunately this year the moon will be fairly bright at 87% of its full moon level.

President's Message (cont.)

There is one comet of interest: the interstellar object 3I/Atlas, but this is currently at magnitude 16.5. It will be in its closest approach to Earth on October 29.

With respect to deep space objects there are still many opportunities. The constellation Cygnus is a good source of targets, for example, the Eastern and Western Veil nebulas, the Crescent nebula, and several star clusters. The Dumbbell nebula (M27) is a popular target in the constellation Vulpecula. The great cluster (M13) in Hercules is also in good position now. Finally, the constellation Ophiuchus contains many colorful objects and molecular clouds.

Observatory Way

August 2025

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for the Roane State Tamke Allan Observatory. Traveling west, the sign is on the left as you turn into Observatory Way from Caney Creek Road, just past Joiner Hollow Road.

TAO Public Stargazes and Special Events

TAO offers Public Stargazes to the community on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month, weather permitting. Our usual schedule for the summer is to open at 8:30 pm and continue to nominally 10:30 pm -- later when the sky and attendance encourage this. Opening time changes according to the season, and a good guide is to arrive at the observatory about sunset, when weather is encouraging. These stargazes are supported by local astronomy clubs, especially ORION members and friends, and benefit our students and community. Our TAO stargazes are usually well-attended, with a full classroom of visitors for evening astronomy lectures.

Our next TAO stargaze is Aug. 16, near the peak of a rather minor meteor shower, the kappa Cygnids. There probably won't be many meteors, but when they do appear they are often bright fireballs.

Adding the beauty of mathematics to our TAO Astronomy mix: July 22-23

Our astrophotos show much beauty. Sometimes the beauty in Physics and Astronomy is in the symmetry and evolving complexity of nature. We don't get so much into the 'higher' mathematics at TAO, but analysis of the July 22-23 data from the occultation with asteroid 1776 Kuiper showed that careful thinking (including the mathematics) can show some beauty and enhance our understanding. See the article on how to interpret this occultation data (elsewhere in this issue) to appreciate the fun of the analysis.

Those of us participating in our July Occultation event saw some nice people working together. Thanks to Don Spong for the following three photos. The first photo shows Ted and Rob discussing LX-200 operation. I spent some time working on this telescope with Rob also (in the end, the telescope and mount performed well). The last two photos show Don and Ted (perhaps present, but not necessarily) at their work stations.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Pondering the Meade LX-200. Note Scorpius and Antares at upper right.

Images from the July 22-23 July 2025 Dark Stargaze at TAO.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Our International Friendship Stargazes

TAO Astronomers support our Astronomy Classes, our Public Stargazes, and our Special Events. Examples of special events are eclipses, planetary transits across the sun, and Asteroid Occultations. A recurring special event is our monthly "International Friendship Stargaze" which is held during the week of the first quarter moon at the Bissell Park "International Friendship Bell" in Oak Ridge.

The last week in August ushers in a 1st Quarter moon, and an opportunity for an International Friendship Stargaze" so we can add that to our calendar.

International Visitors

We expect International visitors at TAO and at our International Friendship Stargazes. Sometimes our skies are graced by Interstellar visitors. Comet 3I/Atlas is one such visitor. It is now in our sky, but is dim. It will be closest to the sun on Oct. 29, where it will be in orbit between Earth and Mars. It is probably from a region of older stars, so would be older than the Earth. Wouldn't it be exciting to get a sample?

3III/ATLAS was discovered by an observatory in Chile, partially funded by NASA. But NASA projects, along with many research, health-related, educational, and (all) climate-related activities, are being diminished (some say destroyed) by our government. It appears that anything remotely difficult to understand is subject to being deemed unimportant by our current government. Surely the situation isn't that bad?

Of course not. Almost certainly not. It's just that one must apparently have the correct political view to be supported, even if the goals and quality are present. Surely the situation isn't that bad?

New ORION Astronomy display at AMSE in Oak Ridge

We have a new, inspiring Astronomy display at the American Museum of Science and Energy! This deserves a photo, but Ted says that it will appear on the cover this month. So, enjoy! Or even better, visit AMSE and have a personal look at our new multi-dimensional display!

ORION Board Meetings ElCantarito

- Rob Fowler

This is a summary of topics discussed recently at the weekly (Monday 1 pm) ORION Board Meeting held as a regular working lunch at ElCantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge. Notes as contributed in Stardate format by Sec. Rob Fowler.

Stardate: 2025.03.31

In attendance were Robert Fowler, Ted Barnes, David Fields, Art Alison and Don Spong. Discussed delays on new dome report due to committee participant availability. Discussed possible going to TAO Tuesday night. Discussed next speaker is not firm for April's meeting. Discussed voting for officers at the next ORION Meeting. Discussed the next Friendship Stargaze and date for same, 8th possibly. Discussed possibly coming up with cloudy night entertainment for Friendship stargaze. Discussed Wordsworth poem about telescopes. Discussed potential security cams for TAO.

Stardate: 2025.04.07

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes and Rob Fowler. Ted discussed the data acquired from his Arduino/LED test. David discussed a mount having the ability to track asteroids via PHD2. David discussed the Friendship Stargaze is 7:30pm Tuesday. Discussed needing pics of new concrete pads at TAO.

Stardate: 2025.04.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob. Ted discussed results of the 785 Zwetana occultation. After a long and dramatic story, Ted revealed a successful capture. Noah is reaching out to Joe Baldwin about next month's presentation. Ted discussed quantum field theory using functional methods.

Stardate: 2025.04.21

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Noah Frere and Rob Fowler. Ted discussed how to use AnyDesk and log in unattended. Ted discussed a planetary occultation, Mars vs a 9th magnitude star on May 6th at 1 am. David discussed progress he is making with a Meshtastic receiver. Mention of 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson. David brought up calendar access .Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axels. One axle migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.04.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Kevin Wilson, John Cliff and Rob Fowler. Briefly mentioned domes on CloudyNights.com. Ted discussed upcoming Mars/Star occultation and relevant challenges. HD 74058 vs Mars just after midnight 00:44 night 5th/6th morn. TAO Stargaze beginning at May 3rd 8pm. Friendship Stargaze possibly May 6th. Briefly discussed avoiding Feynman's van. Shared astrophotos. Discussed potentially going to TAO tonight & Noah's class.

Stardate: 2025.05.05

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes, Kevin Wilson, and Rob Fowler. David asked if we have a set program for May. That remains unclear. Ted contacted Noah to confirm. We await a reply. Ted mentioned the next annual IOTA meeting is possibly going to be in New Mexico in Oct.

Stardate: 2025.05.12

At 11am David, Ted & Art met at the Library and made a first pass at setting up a display case for the club. Rob joined later. It was artistically done, decorated with a small telescope, some antique books, and astrophotos. Discussed whether Kevin might give the May lecture and what topics he has ready. He agreed to speak on the topic of stellar spectroscopy. Ted mentioned the next possible occultation on the early morning on 5/21/2025.

Stardate: 2025.05.19

In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob. Kevin brought up Benjamin Baniker as a potential lecturer. Rob announced that the most recent lecture is on YouTube.

Star Date: 2025.05.26

In attendance were Don, Dave, Art & Rob. David suggested improvements to the Meade's power supply in hopes of reducing noise, higher amperage power supply, adding ferrite cores. Dave discussed getting a construction party to begin construction on the Dob shelter. Discussed parking issues at TAO.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.06.02

In attendance were Don, David, Bob, Art, Juan, Kevin and Noah (and Sunny). We met early at the library to discuss the current and new display box. Discussed meeting again, tomorrow (Tuesday). David suggested Wednesday night 8:30pm as the next Friendship Stargaze. Kevin suggested meeting at TAO to look at the Meade's encoder. Noah suggested reaching out to Gareth Davis to see if he has any potential acquaintances for another lecture. Don asked about the new dome project. David responded with a tale of woe regarding the Roane purchasing project.

Stardate: 2025.06.09

In attendance were Don, David, Art and Rob (joined by John Rather). David purchased 2 coin cells for the Celestron CGM mount. He also purchased a few ferrite cores to suppress noise from the power supply. Ted expressed an interest in having help with this months Trapezium. Discussed the new optical telescope coming online in the Atacama Desert. Briefly mentioned the library displays and Oak Ridge street lighting. Noah mentioned that Gareth Davis can give the next lecture.

Stardate: 2025.06.16

In attendance were Don, Kevin, Art and Rob. Rob showed his submission for the AMSE poster. Kevin & Don discussed PixInsight. We confirmed Kevin is speaking this month. Kevin discussed the Astronomical League and it's various programs, and contests for various achievements.

Stardate: 2025.06.23

Due to crowding at the table, no notes were taken. In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin and Robert.

Stardate: 2025.06.30

In attendance were David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob. Don sat in for a short while. Ted & Rob discussed results of the occultation via a new process. Kevin presented a new ORION Logo. Kevin announced he will be moving out of the immediate area.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.06.30 (cont.)

David presented Kevin with a gift ORION T-Shirt. David brought up shop type measurements he intends to do on the Meade. The group went on discuss various theoretical topics. Mention of 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson David brought up calendar access. Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axels. One axel migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

Stardate: 2025.07.07

In attendance were Don, Ted, David, Art, Rob and visitor John Rather. Conversations opened with Ted discussing digitizing the occultation substacking project. David discussed a lightstrip project and possible application in the dome. Ted collected info for this month's Trapezium. David discussed attendance at the Sat July 5 Public Star Gaze, was 12, give or take. David discussed the testing we did on the Meade and saw no alignment errors.

Stardate: 2025.07.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob. Ted shared some mathematical analysis of the recent occultation data. David brought up potential dates for the next Friendship Star Gaze. We discussed the next ORION lecture and whether to zoom it or not. We discussed possibly having a news feature at ORION lectures.

Stardate: 2025.07.21

In attendance were David, Don, Ted, Art, Rob... and guest John. Dave led the discussion with Rob's absence. Dave mentioned that Saturday night's public star gaze was successful, with around 8 visitors. We discussed the recent lecture and the unplanned move to the computer classroom. The general consensus is that it went well. Dave will be away on August 2nd, the next star gaze. Ted brought up details of participation in the Tuesday night / Wednesday morning occultation.

Stardate: 2025.07.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison and Rob Fowler We will probably have a public star gaze at TAO on 8/2/2025, public or private depending on weather and Noah's decision. 8/12/2025 Perseid meteor shower a probable star gaze.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.07.28 (cont.)

Our Library display will expire soon. David will inquire if we can keep it another month or if we need to clean it out this month. If it has to come down, Ted & Rob have agreed to remove the contents.

Stardate: 2025.08.05

Present were Don, Ted, Rob, Art and guest John Rather. Ted shared his most recent results and submission to IOTA that we have been re-evaluating. Don won't be present for the August ORION meeting. We believe John Cliff is August's speaker. We discussed various lightning phenomenon We also discussed the Big Bang theory and John Rather's book.

Stardate: 2025.08.11

Present were Don, Ted, David, Art, Rob and guests Richard Piety and John Rather. Ted reported on some of his recent results with IOTA's python scripts and graphing. Rob reported on visiting Lily Bluff's Star Party at Wartburg, where he met Joshua, Gareth and Owen. Don told us of a new 16 bit color astro camera he just bought, a ZWO ASI2600MCP. John told us of an experience with a pro telescope. Richard just bought a QHY174MGPS camera for recording timed asteroid occultations. We discussed weather regarding the Perseid meteor / stargaze, 8:30pm Tuesday, but the weather is deteriorating. There is a possible occultation on 8/23/25.

ORION Monthly Meetings

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Meeting Venue: City Room (A-111), just inside the main entrance, Coffey/McNalley Bldg., Oak Ridge Campus, Roane State Community College.

7:00 pm Eastern, 3rd Wednesday of each month.

Our monthly meetings (except for December, a dinner) generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited Presentation and Discussion
- Awarding of the Mug
- Astrophotography / Special Presentations

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm Eastern, on the 3rd Wednesday of the month. The beginning of the meeting will usually include announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9:00 pm. Please plan to stay until the end. Hopefully we will all enjoy the astrophotography and other special topics discussed in the latter part of the meeting.

Remote Viewing: A live Zoom session will usually be open during the ORION Monthly Meeting, at the link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or
<https://bit.ly/42apGxX>

Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

Title: Geochemical Evidence of Life on Mars

Speaker: Dr. John Cliff

*First image from the Viking 1 Mars lander.
NASA image PIA00381.*

Abstract:

There is yet to be a consensus opinion on a definition of life. Nevertheless, some characteristics of life include, organization, metabolism, homeostasis, growth, reproduction, response to stimuli, and evolution. Despite the near statistical certainty of extant life throughout the universe, definitive evidence of extraterrestrial life has yet to be found. Active avenues of past and present inquiry include remote sensing and spectroscopy and *in situ* measurements of meteorites found on Earth and via robotic probes. Mars has received considerable attention with regard to exploring geochemical signatures for life in both meteorites found terrestrially and via remote probes sent to the Martian surface. This talk will explore types of biosignatures that may be useful from the standpoint of remote probes using terrestrial examples and then focus on the evidence for Life on Mars from meteorites and *in situ* experiments conducted on the Martian regolith.

Title: Geochemical Evidence of Life on Mars

Speaker: Dr. John Cliff

Mini Bio:

John's formal academic training includes an MS degree in Environmental Microbiology from West Virginia University, and a doctorate in Soil Science from Oregon State University. John was the first person to apply secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) to explore process-level biogeochemistry in soil systems at sub-millimeter scales. He has since become a recognized authority on the use of this specialized analytical technique.

During his tenure at Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL) in the mid 2000s he helped to develop SIMS methodologies for nuclear and microbial forensic applications. Cliff spent a year as a Cost-Free Expert at the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) in Seibersdorf, Austria in 2007, followed by tenures at two scientific user facilities including the Australian Microscopy and Microanalysis Research Facility at the University of Western Australia (UWA) and the Environmental Molecular Sciences Laboratory (EMSL), upon returning to PNNL.

While at UWA, Cliff served as Technical Lead in the university's successful bid to become a member of the IAEA's Network of Analytical Laboratories for the detection of undeclared nuclear materials. UWA is still the only university to achieve NWAL qualification.

Cliff began work at Oak Ridge National Laboratory in late 2023 where he continues his work developing SIMS methodologies targeting nuclear nonproliferation applications. Cliff became an avid amateur astro-photographer while living in Washington state, and currently is building an observatory on his property near Kingston, Tennessee.

ORION Last Month

Asteroid Occultations

- Ted Barnes

Our featured speaker for the July 2025 ORION Presentation was ORION member Ted Barnes. Ted is a graduate of Caltech, where he did his PhD in Theoretical Physics, specializing in the study of strongly interacting particles composed of quarks and gluons. His advisor was Jon Mathews, and he received additional assistance on his thesis work from Richard Feynman. After several postdoctoral positions he accepted a permanent position as the first ORNL-UTK Collaborating Scientist, and was a staff member here in the ORNL Physics Div and the UTK Dept of Physics and Astronomy from 1989-2011. He was a Detailee at DOE HQ in Germantown, Md from 2008, and from 2011-2018 was a full time Program Manager in the Office of Nuclear Physics at DOE HQ. He retired from DOE in 2018 and returned to the Oak Ridge area, where he joined ORION in 2019.

Ted had originally suggested a shorter contribution on the more obscure topic of Planetary Occultations, based on an attempt to record a Mars occultation at TAO on 06 May 2025. The talk was called “Mars or Bust,” and despite the careful technical planning it really was a bust, due to the weather. Noah instead invited a full hour ORION talk, and after asking several people what topic they would prefer, Ted prepared a summary talk on Asteroids and Asteroid Occultations for Wed 16 July 2025. This included an introduction to three asteroids, 253 Matilde, 433 Eros, and 101955 Benu, followed by a summary of asteroid occultations and how to image them, the 11 occultations we have completed in ORION and reported to IOTA to date, a discussion of a new technique developed for imaging fainter target stars, and a list of future prospects for studying asteroids at TAO.

NASA's OSIRIS-REx
visited fm 3 Dec 2018
Samples Oct 2020
Sample return Sep 2023

$V_{esc} = 20$ cm/sec

$m_v = 23.5$
in Virgo
 $d_E = 1.18$ AU

101955 Benu

"PHA"
Potentially Hazardous Asteroid
= Comes within 0.05AU of Earth's orbit.

Tohen class **F**
C carbonaceous, subtype F
S stony
X metallic

mean diam. 0.49 km

rubble pile asteroid

$T_{rot} = 4.2905 \pm 0.0065$ hrs

By NASA/Goddard/University of Arizona - File:Benu mosaic OSIRIS-REx.jpg from <https://www.nasa.gov/press-release/nasa-spacecraft-provides-insight-into-asteroid-benu-s-future-orbit>, Public Domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=138720616>

101955 Benu, an example of a “rubble-pile” asteroid, only about 0.5 km in diameter.

ORION Last Month

Asteroid Occultations (cont.)

David Fields thanks Ted Barnes for his ORION presentation on Asteroid Occultations, Wed 16 July 2025.

Events and Calendars, Sky Maps and Occultations

Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025

We enthusiastically invite visitors to attend our Public Stargaze events, held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee. These events are intended especially for visitors, so our buildings and facilities will be open, and there will be astronomy talks as well as public skywatching.

In Jan-Jun 2025 we plan to hold fixed-calendar public Stargaze events on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These weekend events are especially appropriate for families. We also hold public special events, such as a “Full Moonrise,” with associated Moon Music, and the occasional comet watch. The annual Perseid Meteor watch in mid-August is especially popular.

The precise dates of many of these events depend on the local weather conditions, and cannot be specified *definitively* long in advance. As an approximate guide, see the TAOCalendar pages following. Once a date is finalized we usually confirm it through the ORION online message site ORION astronomy@groups.io. Likely and unlikely dates for TAO events may be inferred from the weather predictions at TAO by Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com).

Please confirm event dates before proceeding to TAO.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, “Observatory Way,” first-time visitors should plan to arrive before dark. Driving instructions are given at: <https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/visit.htm>

Some instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with procedures for stargazing at a dark-sky site.

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their telescopes and mounts, to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please bring a red flashlight, or a headband with a red-light option.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or red-light headbands for observing may find them at many commercial amateur astronomy sites, such as [https:// www dot high pointscientific dot com](https://www.highpointscientific.com). The “Lepro LE” LED Headlamp, model 3200008, available from Amazon for about \$10 (Aug. 2024) is a personal favorite. This is rechargeable and has separate red and white led buttons, with several brightness settings. A caution: For amateur astronomy, brighter lights are NOT preferred, and WHITE lights are highly discouraged. Please use only red lights while the Stargaze is in progress.

Parking is available on site; on entering TAO **stay to the right**, and *please use the parking area below and right (Southwest) of the TAO buildings and observing area, near the treeline*. And **PLEASE NO HEADLIGHTS ON SITE.**

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are welcome to coffee and other refreshments.

TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025

In 2025 we are reverting to an earlier schedule of having our Public Stargaze nights on every first and third Saturday. Of course this assumes good weather; if the weather is not suitable, a changed schedule will be announced on the group site [ORIONastronomy @ groups.io](mailto:ORIONastronomy@groups.io).

We decided that the previous (2024) schedule of a once-monthly Public Stargaze was insufficient, and having a Moon visible in some phase other than close to New gives our visitors an obvious and interesting object for viewing.

During Daylight Savings Time (mid-March through early November) we plan to hold our Public Stargaze events over the hours of approximately 8:00 pm - 11:00 pm, with some nominal variation.

If it is already dark when you arrive, please dim your headlights on the TAO grounds, follow the right branch of the access road, and park to the right of the TAO building, near the treeline.

Note: Parking in or near the elevated flat observing area at the front (East) of the TAO building is reserved for astronomers who are bringing their equipment.

Additional information for visitors may be found on the previous page and following two pages of this issue.

TAO Public Stargazes in July & August:

Sats 19 Jul & 2 Aug 2025

Sat 19 Jul 2025

Sunset	8:54 pm
Civ dusk	9:23 pm
Ast dusk	10:37 pm
Moonrise	01:25 am
Moonset	4:08 pm

Moon illum. 35%

No Moon during this event.

Sat 02 Aug 2025

Sunset	8:43 pm
Civ dusk	9:11 pm
Ast dusk	10:21 pm
Moonrise	3:30 pm
Moonset*	1:18 am

*03 Aug

Moon illum. 59%

Waxing Gibbous Moon during this event.
Cancelled due to overcast.

TAO Public Stargazes later in August:

Sats 16 & 30 Aug 2025

Sat 16 Aug 2025

Sunset	8:28 pm
Civ dusk	8:55 pm
Ast dusk	10:01 pm
Moonrise	00:51 am
Moonset	3:12 pm

Moon illum. 58%

No Moon during this event.

Sat 30 Aug 2025

Sunset	8:09 pm
Civ dusk	8:35 pm
Ast dusk	9:39 pm
Moonrise	2:18 pm
Moonset	11:52 pm

Moon illum. 43%

Waxing Crescent Moon during this event.

TAO Calendars

Jan-Jun 2025; Jul & Aug 2025

The principle public events for visitors at TAO are the **Public Stargazes**, held at TAO during 2025 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These are listed in the “**Public Fixed Events**” **TAO Calendar** for six month periods, currently Jul-Dec 2025. These appear on the page following.

Additional notable events will be included in monthly “**Special Events**” **TAO Calendars**. These include public events that do not have a fixed date long in advance, such as the **International Friendship Stargaze** in Oak Ridge, and special TAO events such as **Asteroid Occultations, Meteor Showers, Full Moonrises, Lunar (and other) Eclipses, Comet Watches**, and perhaps the occasional musical event.

These “Special Events” calendars for the current and subsequent months appear after the six-month “Public Fixed Events” calendar.

The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during the “Public Fixed Events,” and will also usually be available when TAO is open to the public for some of the “Special Events.” **Please inquire regarding whether TAO will be open to the public for any “Special Event” you may wish to attend, since some may be restricted.** We will of course always try to accommodate enthusiastic visitors.

We recommend checking a TAO website such as **ORIONastronomy @ groups.io** before visiting, to confirm that listed events will proceed as planned; weather conditions for example may require a cancellation or change of date.

TAO Calendar Public Stargaze

Jan-Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Feb 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Feb 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 19 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 03 May 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 17 May 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 07 Jun 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter and Spring, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAO Calendar Public Stargaze

Jul-Dec 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 05 Jul 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 19 Jul 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 02 Aug 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 16 Aug 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 06 Sep 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 20 Sep 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 04 Oct 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 18 Oct 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 01 Nov 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Nov 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 06 Dec 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 20 Dec 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAOCalendar Special Events

Jul 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Thu 03 Jul 2025	★	International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	8:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 05 Jul 2025	★	1st Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Thu 10 Jul 2025	○	Full Moon 04:36 pm Eastern		
Sat 19 Jul 2025	★	3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Wed 23 Jul 2025	★	Occultation 1776 Kuiper	00:38:17	00:38:19
Thu 24 Jul 2025	●	New Moon 03:11 pm Eastern		

TAOCalendar Special Events

Aug 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 02 Aug 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	8:30 pm	10:30 pm
Ddd dd Aug 2025		International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	8:00 pm	10:00 pm
Wed 09 Aug 2025		Full Moon 03:54 am Eastern		
Tue 12 Aug 2025		Perseid Meteor Shower	8:30 pm	late
Sat 16 Aug 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:30 pm	10:30 pm
Wed 23 Aug 2025		New Moon 02:06 am Eastern		

The day of 19 July 2025 was quite mixed, with periods of overcast followed by bright sunlight. The predicted weather for TAO appeared rather unattractive, with overcast and perhaps rain in the evening, followed by possible clearing after midnight. Despite this prediction David suggested that we continue with the Public Stargaze in any case, since we do have occasional visitors even on evenings too cloudy for observing.

I somehow arrived too early, at 7:40 pm, and spent my wait at the TAO gate checking my earlier astronomy computing records for 2024 and 2025. David arrived close to 8:00 pm and we went inside, followed shortly by Art Allison. I did hear from a few potential visitors by cell phone. Robert Corliss appeared soon after 8:00 pm.

I meanwhile tried a test AD connection to my home observatory, which went through successfully to the lab but not to my office computer. I only managed that as a two-step AD connection through my lab computer. This “snag” has since been addressed.

A view of sunset and mixed clouds to the West, 9:10 pm, 19 Jul 2025.

Public Stargaze of Sat 19 July 2025 (cont.)

As the evening darkened the overcast thickened; when our first set of visitors arrived they assured us that they had seen several stars outside, perhaps as many as four. We mainly chatted about what we did at TAO to promote astronomy, and then gave them a quick tour of the 8" reflector and the 14" Meade in the dark, warm, moist night. They did enjoy seeing the two large telescopes, and climbing the ladder inside the dome.

Astronomy discussions in the TAO classroom, followed by a climb in the dome to see the 8" refractor. 8:50 - 9:00 pm, 19 Jul 2025.

After our two groups of visitors departed, since the sky appeared to be stubbornly overcast, our four ORION members present (David, Art, Robert C. and Ted) assembled our materials and departed from TAO about 10:20 pm. A less than successful night for observing, but a contribution to public outreach, even on such a Dark and Stormy Night.

Occultation by Asteroid 1776 Kuiper at TAO on 23 Jul 2025.

- Ted Barnes

After our challenging observation of the occultation of a faint target star (g-mag 13.6) by asteroid 621 Werdandi on 21 Jun 2025, it was reassuring to see a much brighter target star approaching in the TAO-accessible Occult Watcher list, this being the occultation of the 11.1 g-mag star UCAC4 427-122587 by the 16.1 mag main-belt asteroid 1776 Kuiper, in the dim constellation Aquarius. The predicted event's midpoint time was 00:38:18 Eastern on Wed 23 Jul 2025, with a time error estimate of 0.4 secs, and a predicted max dur of 4.2 secs.

The only obvious complication with recording this event was that TAO was near the edge of the predicted shadow path, at 27.3 km from the shadow center line. (The shadow edge was expected to be at 33.0 km from the center line.) Assuming a spherical asteroid, we expected the duration of the occultation at our location to be reduced by a factor of 0.56, from 4.2 secs to 2.4 secs.

Based on past experience I usually assemble a standard set of four documents for a new occultation, obtained from Occult Watcher, JPL Horizons, and TheSkyX. These are 1) occultation data, from OW; 2) an orbit diagram, from JPL Horizons, 3) a sky chart showing constellations, generated using TheSkyX, and 4) a local shadow path, from OW. The documents are shown on the four pages following the next page. To assist observers I also usually prepare a more detailed star and asteroid chart, scaled approximately to the field of view of the observer.

Gerard Kuiper

Kuiper in 1964

Born	Gerrit Pieter Kuiper 7 December 1905 Tuitjenhorn, Netherlands
Died	23 December 1973 (aged 68) Mexico City, Mexico
Nationality	Dutch–American
Alma mater	Leiden University
Occupations	Astronomer · planetary scientist · selenographer · author · professor

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

We began following the weather forecasts about a week in advance, and both CSC and Astrospheric continued to say good things about the night of 22-23 Jul 2025. (A predicted 6 hrs of clear sky centered on the event was reasonably persistent, and seemed almost too good to be true.) Having discussed this event at our weekly Monday 21 July ElCantarito ORION Board Meeting we decided to proceed, and agreed to a Dark Stargaze at TAO on 22-23 July. After the usual confusion regarding details, four ORION members, Rob, Don, Ted and David appeared at TAO on Tue 22 Jul 2025, at 8:00 pm or shortly after. Sunny the Astrodog, recovering from a medical concern, was also present at TAO, and happily accepted a ham and cheese roll.

The ElCantarito ORION Board Meeting of Mon 21 July 2025, at which the Dark Stargaze of Tue-Wed 22-23 July 2025 with asteroid occultation was approved. Clockwise from left, David Fields, Don Spong, John Rather, Art Allison and Rob Fowler. Image by Ed.

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

Prediction

Last Updated: 02/Jul/25, 17:03 UT

Data Sources: Horizons/GaiaDR3

Error (path widths): 0.020

Err. Ellipse: 0.0025" x 0.0003"

Err. Basis: Known errors

Computed By: OWC

Orbit Date: 30 Jun 2025 (JPL#67)

Error in time: 0.4 sec

Err. Ellipse PA: 77°

OWC Id: 2478403

Event

From: 04:29:05 UT

Combined Mag: 10.36

Mag Drop (V): 5.23

Shadow Width: 66.5 km

Solar Elong.: 152°

To: 04:42:24 UT

Max Duration: 4.2 sec

Mag Drop (R): 5.09

Moon Phase: 3% sunlit

Moon Elong.: 131°

Target Star

Name: UCAC4 427-122587

Constellation: Aquarius

Diameter: 0.10 mas (Gaia)

RUWE: 1.05

Gaia SourceId:

2669885777252849920

RA [ICRS]: 21^h 45^m 51^s.3017

Dec [ICRS]: -04° 40' 28".885

V mag: 11.08

R mag: 10.37

B mag: 11.65

Flags:

Gaia Flags:

RA [aprnt]: 21^h 47^m 12^s.8552

Dec [aprnt]: -04° 33' 19".696

Parameters relating to the occultation, extracted from Occult Watcher.

Object

Name: (1776) Kuiper

Diameter: 41.3 ± 2 km (Occult)

Distance: 2.2265 au

Motion RA: -20.45 "/hr

Moons: 0

Class: Main-belt Asteroid

Diameter (augm): 25.67 mas

Mag: 16.1 ▲

Motion Dec: -8.76 "/hr

Rings: 0

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

A JPL Horizons orbit diagram showing the orbit (white line) and position (white dot and label) of asteroid 1776 Kuiper between the orbits of Mars (red line) and Jupiter (orange line) at the time of the occultation, just past midnight (00:38 am Eastern), on 23 Jun 2025.

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

A large scale sky chart at the time predicted for the occultation, generated using TheSkyX. Here one can see the location of the asteroid 1776 Kuiper and the target star UCAC4 427-122587 in the dim constellation Aquarius (purple). The star and asteroid are denoted by a red circle and crosshair, near the image center.

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

OW Cloud

(1776) Kuiper occults UCAC4 427-122587 on 23 Jul 2025

Change prediction: [default] Horizons/GaiaDR3, last upd: 02 Jul, 17:03 by OWC, orbit date: 30 Jun 2025 (JPL#67)

Path of the asteroid's shadow (R -> L) across East Tennessee. TAO (base of the scope icon, with a white tangent line) is rather close to the shadow's edge (blue), and far from the centerline (green), so this event should be rather shorter than the predicted max dur of 4.2 secs, about 2.4 secs if we assume a spherical asteroid. The predicted midpoint time was 00:38:18 Eastern. A second observer is positioned on the orange tangent line. Our position on the shadow profile (pale blue) is indicated by a black tick mark near the right edge.

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

On arrival at TAO about 8 pm Eastern the sky was a striking clear blue, with almost no evidence of clouds. Of course this didn't last, and by 9 pm we saw a scattering of clouds in various directions, as seen below in these images to the West and North, both at 9:10 pm Eastern.

My standard setup for capturing asteroid occultations, showing the view to the West. Every observing session has its share of difficulties; on this evening I went through three green laser pointers, with each failing after an initial promising few minutes of operation.

Don Spong setting up on the popular North Pad. His expressed interest during this Dark Stargaze was in imaging the Cat's Eye Nebula, NGC 6543, a planetary nebula in Draco. An image is included in this month's Astrophotography section.

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

Rob Fowler preparing the Meade LX-200 for what proved to be a successful attempt to capture the occultation by 1776 Kuiper. The results of this run showed that capturing faster frames that are needed to give more precise results for occultation timing will likely require improved fine focus control. Adding PHD2 guiding would also be a useful modification. This image is also from 9:10 pm Eastern, 22 Jul 2025.

Once my system was completely assembled, I decided that doing a new alignment was probably a good idea. Note: Although the three pictures of TAO above look pleasant enough, the evening was actually stuffy, very warm, humid, unpleasant, and moderately rich in insects. A light breeze at 9:25 pm was such a nice change that I made a note of it. Next I powered on the CGX and CPWI, checked coordinates, pointed the laser at Polaris, and began a manual align. The laser was surprisingly close to Polaris, so it quickly went out. I replaced it with a 2nd laser that had been on my Mak-Newt. It too quickly went out. I borrowed a third laser from Rob, and continued. I aligned the CGX platform on Polaris as a start (well why not), turned SharpCap on, and tried to focus the QHY174MGPS camera. It needed more drawback space from the RC, the existing focus tube was a bit short. This was a familiar problem, and is the reason I had recently ordered a new 50mm long 2" diameter Svbony extension tube, which I had actually remembered to pack. It was perfect, and gave me another *ca.* 1-2" of draw length, so I could bring the QHY into focus. I chose a few faint stars and set the SharpCap screen on maximum magnification, (800%) and 1/60 sec exposure, and reduced the faint star images to a few pixels square.

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

With PHD2 guiding on (so I could find my first alignment star in the wide field 60mm guide scope), I slewed to Kochab, and had an initial struggle with it, because as usual after a long bumpy van ride and a reassembly, the laser pointer, OTA and guide scope were not at all well mutually aligned. Once they were all pointing in the same direction I aligned on Kochab, and then continued with Alioth, Aldebaran, Deneb and Altair. Somewhere around Altair the 3rd laser went out (and that's a great line for a Sci-Fi novel), but by then I was well enough aligned that long slews repeatedly gave me the desired star in the OTA. Working towards Aquarius I added Enif, and then for fun I finished with Sadalmelik (Happiness of the King) in the Water Jug, and Sadalsuud (Happiness of the South). Yes, in Arabic, "Sad" means happy. CPWI noted that my polar alignment could be improved, but I decided to ignore that. To the naked eye this part of the sky was quite murky (we had bands of mist crossing Scorpius and Sagittarius), and the faint stars of Aquarius were barely visible, but in the OTA the latter two alignment stars were clear. Next I slewed to the target star, at RA 21 45 51 and Dec -04 40 29. I recognized the field as correct from my hand drawing; it was out of center by a part of the f.o.v., but was close enough that I forgot to have SharpCap do a final plate solve to improve my field. That was about 11:00 pm. I next turned PHD2 loose with multistar guiding, and it did very well. The GPS remained locked. Most surprisingly, I had no serious system problems in the run-up to the 00:38 am event.

Not long before the occultation I captured a reference image, during the period 23:09:17 - 23:21:25 pm. This stack of 183x4sG480 frames, post-processed, is shown on the following page. This was plate-solved using the program ASPS. The target star is at middle right, and the asteroid 1776 Kuiper is visible just above and left of the target star as it approaches. Their coordinates and the observed coordinates for the field stars with indicated g-magnitudes are consistent with Gaia positions, but of course with much lower accuracy. The limiting magnitude in this image is approximately 19.5.

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

Above: Detail from an ASPS (plate solved) image of the target star UCAC4 427-122587, the approaching asteroid 1776 Kuiper, and some field stars. This is an enlarged version of a reference stack of 183x4sG480 frames, captured by the QHY174MGPS camera during 23:09:17 - 23:21:25 pm Eastern 22 Jul 2025, post processed for brightness and contrast, with a blue tint added. SP = “stuck pixel.” The f.o.v. is 16.2’x11.0’. Some star g-magnitudes from Gaia are noted.

The plate-solved coordinates we find for 1776 Kuiper are RA 21 45 53.5-53.0 and Dec -04 40 17, in agreement with a JPL Horizons Ephemeris to within about 0.1s of RA and 1” of Dec.

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

For the occultation itself I decided to use 50 ms for frame exposures (a program I had written to recommend exposures suggested about 70 ms), and I cut the field size back to 640x480, so as not to lose time in processing and copying a long sequence of large frames. I repeatedly noted that the sky was murky, with bands of mist to the S and SE. (This event was in the SE, at Alt@Azi = 34°@127°.) The ambient temperature was very close to the dew point. I changed my imaging plans slightly, and decided to capture 400 frames of 50 ms (20 secs total), starting by hand at 00:38:10 Eastern, nominally 8 secs before the occultation.

In parallel with my efforts, Rob and David had been aligning the Meade LX-200, and all seemed to be going well for them. Rob had found the target star, and asked me to count off the final minutes until 00:38:18. Rob told me that he had difficulty with the fine focus control, and as a result didn't have a sharp target star image. In compensation he decided to be conservative, and used long frames of 500 ms.

So, as the time for the event neared, we both started capturing frames, and then were finished until the frames could be post-processed and carefully inspected. I confirmed that I had 400 frames of 50 ms each, but they appeared quite dark; I could only just see what I assumed was the target star with extreme magnification, as a few faint off-white pixels.

So, we packed up and departed around 1:30 pm; I arrived home at about 2:40 am. Of course I couldn't just go to sleep, I first needed to know whether I had captured the occultation!

An inspection of the first frame of the 400 50ms frames I had captured (next page) showed that prospects for identifying the target star in each frame were encouraging; with post-processing for brightness and contrast (right frame) the target star was easily visible.

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

Raw 1st 50ms frame of 400.

Same after post processing.

Thus all I had to do was to identically post-process the raw frames, and identify the two frames in which the target star is 1) in transition from on to off, and 2) in transition from off to on. These proved to be frames 103 and 153. These had UT time stamps (when the imaging begins, rounding to ms) of 04:38:15.820 and 04:38:18.349. Since the disappearance frame 103 was near full brightness, and 104 was completely extinguished, I assigned a disappearance time of just 10 ms before frame 104, with a rough error estimate of +/- 10 ms; $D = 04:38:15.86(1)$. The reappearance transition frame 153 just shows a very faint reappearing star, so I similarly assigned the reappearance a time of 10 ms before frame 154, also with a rough assumed error of +/- 10 ms; $R = 04:38:18.39(1)$. The difference gives our observed duration,

$$\mathbf{dur = R - D = 2.53(1) \text{ secs}}$$

and the mean of R and D gives our observed midpoint

$$\mathbf{(R+D)/2 = 04:38:17.13(1) \text{ UT .}}$$

Occultation by 1776 Kuiper, 23 July 2025. (cont.)

These results were submitted to IOTA on 26 July 2025.

Our observed midpoint is just 0.9 secs before the predicted midpoint of 00:38:18 Eastern. The duration is well below the predicted maximum of 4.2 secs, but as noted on the first page of this article we expected that duration to be reduced to about 2.4 secs, due to our position near the edge of the asteroid. Of course these errors and R and D times involve some estimates based on the appearance of the two transition frames, but an inaccuracy in either much larger than about 10 ms appears unlikely.

We note in passing that successive frame time stamps are actually about 50.6 ms apart, due to a small 0.6 ms processing and storage time.

This completes our analysis of the occultation of the star UCAC4 427-122587 by 1776 Kuiper; our result for the midpoint was about 0.9 secs earlier than predicted, and our result for the duration was consistent with a reduction in the predicted maximum due to our position near the asteroid's edge. This was a straightforward exercise, especially compared to occultations with a significantly fainter target star. (See last month's discussion of 621 Werdandi for that memorable event, and our new analysis technique developed for it.)

And in closing,

Items forgotten this time, as a reminder:

dew shield

mousepad

a working green laser

dark star lapel pin

The evening Sky Map for August 2025 from skymaps.com.

The Evening Sky Map

FREE* EACH MONTH FOR YOU TO EXPLORE, LEARN & ENJOY THE NIGHT SKY

Sky Calendar – August 2025

Follow us on Bluesky
skymaps.com/bsky/

- 1 First Quarter Moon at 12:40 UT.
- 1 Moon at apogee (farthest from Earth) at 21h UT (distance 404,161km; angular size 29.6').
- 4 Moon near Antares at 0h UT (evening sky). Occultation visible from Antarctica, southern Argentina, southern Chile and Falkland Islands.
- 5 Venus at northernmost declination (22.0°) at 8h UT. Mag. -4.0.
- 7 Asteroid 2 Pallas at opposition at 13h UT. Mag. 9.4.
- 9 Full Moon at 7:56 UT.
- 12 Perseid meteor shower peaks at 0h UT. Peak lasts about 12 hours. Active from July 14 to September 1. Produces swift, bright meteors (50-75 per hour) with persistent trains. Best viewed after midnight.
- 12 Venus 0.9° S of Jupiter at 7h UT (36° from Sun, morning sky). Mags. -4.0 and -1.9.
- 12 Moon near Saturn at 13h UT (morning sky). Mag. 0.8.
- 14 Moon at perigee (closest to Earth) at 18:04 UT (distance 369,288km; angular size 32.4').
- 16 Last Quarter Moon at 5:13 UT.
- 16 Moon near the Pleiades at 17h UT (morning sky).
- 19 Mercury at westernmost elongation at 10h UT (19° from Sun, morning sky). Mag. 0.0.
- 19 Moon near Jupiter at 23h UT (morning sky). Mag. -2.0.
- 20 Moon near Venus at 14h UT (morning sky). Mag. -4.0.
- 23 New Moon at 6:06 UT. Start of lunation 1270.
- 26 Moon near Mars at 15h UT (evening sky). Mag. 1.6.
- 27 Moon near Spica at 12h UT (evening sky). Occultation visible from Antarctica.
- 29 Moon at apogee (farthest from Earth) at 16h UT (distance 404,548km; angular size 29.5').
- 31 First Quarter Moon at 6:24 UT.
- 31 Moon near Antares at 8h UT (evening sky). Occultation visible from Antarctica, south-western New Zealand and Macquarie Island.

More space events and links at <http://Skymaps.com/skycalendar/>
 All times in Universal Time (UT). (USA Eastern Daylight Time – UT – 4 hours.)

Support The Evening Sky Map
 • Helping curious minds to explore the night sky since January 2000 •
Recommended Products for Sky Watchers: skymaps.com/store/
 All sales support the continued production of this free resource

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE AUGUST 2025

SKY MAP SHOWS HOW THE NIGHT SKY LOOKS

EARLY AUG 9 PM
LATE AUG 8 PM
(Add 1 hour for Daylight Savings)
 SKY MAP DRAWN FOR A LATITUDE OF 40° NORTH AND IS SUITABLE FOR LATITUDES UP TO 10° NORTH OR SOUTH OF THIS

- Symbols**
- Galaxy ☁
 - Double Star ●●
 - Variable Star ●
 - Diffuse Nebula ☁
 - Planetary Nebula □
 - Open Star Cluster ○
 - Globular Star Cluster ⊙

Star Magnitudes ●●●●●
 -1 0 1 2 3 4

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Note: a nice interactive sky chart from Sky and Telescope may be found at the link <https://skyandtelescope.org/interactive-sky-chart/>

Astrophotography

Deep Sky: Cat's Eye Nebula

- Don Spong

This is C6, the Cat's Eye Nebula. It is a hexagon-shaped planetary nebula in the northern constellation of Draco that was discovered by William Herschel on February 15, 1786. This image was taken at TAO on the evening of July 22. A 8" Celestron Edge HD was used with an 0.7 focal length reducer with a Bader IR/UV filter. The mount was a ZWO AM5. Imaging and mount were controlled by a ZWO ASI AIR in Live Stacking Mode; 36 images (60 seconds each) were stacked. The camera was my new ZWO2600MCPro, cooled to about -10 degrees C. Guiding was done using an external Orion 60mm scope and a ZWO220MMmini monochrome camera; post processing was done with PixInsight and Adobe Lightroom. This is a fairly dim object , and could have benefited from longer exposure.

I especially like to image peculiar galaxies. The distorted spiral shape of NGC 5560 is caused by gravitational interactions with NGC 5569. This image was taken at TAO on the evening of June 20, and was formed by stacking 90 1-minute exposures. It was done with a Celestron 8" Edge HD with 0.7 focal length reducer and a Bader IR/UV filter. The mount was a ZWO AM5, and everything was controlled by an onboard ASI AIR computer in live stacking mode. The camera was a ZWO 533MCP Pro in Bin1 mode (3008x3008), cooled to about -20 degrees. Post processing was done with PixInsight and Adobe Lightroom. It was during this imaging session that the unusual satellite (airplane?) crossing occurred, as shown on Page Three Astronomy. That image was discarded prior to stacking.

Deep Sky:

- Kevin Wilson

As a parting gift, Kevin provided us with six deep sky images taken recently at TAO using his SCT; last month's Trapezium included three of these images; the final three are presented here. These are the pngs, as received. Kevin's caption is given below each image.

The Bubble Nebula (C11) is an emission nebula in the constellation Cassiopeia. The light comes from ionized hydrogen surrounding a star. The gas absorbs light from the star, then reemits it in the red part of the spectrum. Integration of 45 x 1 minute exposure with UV-IR cutoff filter. Taken June 21.

The Whirlpool Galaxy (M51) a grand-design spiral galaxy in Ursa Major. M51 is interacting with the dwarf galaxy NGC 5195. NGC 5195 is being severely disrupted by the interaction, and its stars and gasses are being flung in all directions. A prominent stream of gases and stars connect the two galaxies. The light green areas have high concentrations of ionized oxygen. Integration of 60 x 1 minute exposures with a UV-IR cutoff filter on June 21 with the addition of 30 x 1 minutes exposures on June 22 with an O-III filter.

The Lagoon Nebula (M8) in Sagittarius, an emission nebula. Integration of 30 x 1 minute exposures with UV-IR cutoff filter on June 22.

Appendices

Astronomy

- tb

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = *exactly* 9 460 730 472 580. 8 km = 63 241. 077 084 ... AU
c = speed of light = *exactly* 299 792 458 m/s = *exactly* ☺ 1 ly/yr.
1 AU = *exactly* 149 597 870. 7 km
1 parsec (pc) = 3. 261 598 ... light years (ly)
1 yr (Julian) = *exactly* 365.25 d = *exactly* 31 557 600 s
1 d = *exactly* 86 400 s

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly
distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 8 kpc ~ 25 kly (considerable uncertainty)

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m *exactly*
 H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 0.5 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{1/5}$ x fainter =	1. 584 893 ... x fainter
+ 1 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{2/5}$ x fainter =	2. 511 886 ... x fainter
+ 2 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{4/5}$ x fainter =	6. 309 ... x fainter
+ 2.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^1 x fainter =	10 x fainter
+ 3 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{6/5}$ x fainter =	15. 848 ... x fainter
+ 4 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{8/5}$ x fainter =	39. 810 ... x fainter
+ 5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^2 x fainter =	100 x fainter
+ 6 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{12/5}$ x fainter =	251. 188 ... x fainter
+ 7.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^3 x fainter =	1000 x fainter
+ 8 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{16/5}$ x fainter =	1584. 893 ... x fainter
+ 10 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^4 x fainter =	10 000 x fainter
+ 20 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^8 x fainter =	100 000 000 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = *exactly* 10^2 x fainter = + 5 change in magnitude
 10^2 x more distant = *exactly* 10^4 x fainter = + 10 change in mag
 10^3 x more distant = *exactly* 10^6 x fainter = + 15 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness as seen from a distance of 10 pc
 M_{abs} (our sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / cm^2 s (Barnes's rule ☺)

Astronomy (cont.)

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate. *Exact* numerical relationships are indicated as such.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = the angle ϕ around the celestial polar axis, usually quoted in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = the angle θ above the celestial equator, usually quoted in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ} \ ' \ ''$); analogous to latitude.

The RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's direction in the sky.

A unit length vector ("unit vector") $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ pointing towards an object in the sky ("on the celestial sphere") in terms of RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\eta} = \cos(\theta) \cos(\phi) \mathbf{x} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \mathbf{y} + \sin(\theta) \mathbf{z} = C(c \mathbf{x} + s \mathbf{y}) + S \mathbf{z}$$

The arc angle Θ_{12} between any two directions in the sky $\boldsymbol{\eta}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_2$ (or any two stars) using the dot product formula and some obvious abbreviations, satisfies

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2) = S_1 S_2 + C_1 C_2 c_{1-2}$$

$$1 \text{ degree} = \pi/180 \text{ radians} = 1.745 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcmin} = \pi/10800 \text{ radians} = 2.909 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcsec} = 1 \text{ asec} = \pi/648000 \text{ radians} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} = 10^{-3} \text{ asec} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ asec} @ 1 \text{ km} = 4.848 \text{ mm}$$

$$1 \text{ asec} @ 1 \text{ AU} = 725.3 \text{ km}$$

$$1 \text{ asec} @ 1 \text{ pc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} @ 1 \text{ kpc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = a simple count of days starting at noon UT on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC. That date and time was the start of Julian Day 0. The current JD can be inferred from the value on the cover of the Trapezium.

The 80 Brightest Stars

The 80 brightest stars (c/o Wikipedia), and their distances from Earth in light years, with errors (from Gaia data, or Simbad if needed as an alternative).

1	Sirius	8.709	0.0054	41	Menkalinan	81.1	0.46
2	Canopus	309.	16.	42	Atria	390.6	7.0
3	alpha Centauri A	4.395	0.0083	43	Alhena	109.3	8.2
4	Arcturus	36.72	0.22	44	Peacock	178.8	5.1
5	Vega	25.04	0.069	45	Alsephina	80.6	0.78
6	Capella	42.81	0.26	46	Mirzam	492.7	16.4
7	Rigel	863.	78.	47	Polaris	432.6	6.3
8	Procyon	11.46	0.051	48	Alphard	180.3	1.8
9	Archenar	139.4	3.4	49	Hamal	65.8	0.33
10	Betelgeuse	498.	63.	50	Diphda	96.3	0.46
11	beta Centauri	392.	24.	51	Mizar	81.1	0.93
12	Altair	16.73	0.049	52	Nunki	227.8	4.6
13	alpha Crucis	322.	16.	53	Menkent	58.8	0.21
14	Aldebaran	66.64	1.05	54	Alpheratz	97.0	1.01
15	Antares	554.	94.	55	Mirach	197.4	6.7
16	Spica	250.	13.	56	Rasalhague	48.6	0.77
17	Pollux	33.78	0.09	57	Algieba	130.1	2.7
18	Fomalhaut	25.13	0.09	58	Kochab	130.9	0.63
19	Deneb	1410	200	59	Saiph	974.	37.
20	Mimosa	279.	23.	60	Denebola	35.9	0.21
21	Regulus	79.30	0.67	61	Algol	89.9	3.47
22	Adhara	405.	7.0	62	Tiaki	177.0	4.0
23	Castor	50.68	0.032	63	Muhlifain	130.2	1.5
24	Shaula	571.2	7.5	64	Aspidiske	765.6	18.0
25	Gacrux	88.56	0.43	65	Suhail	544.5	10.0
26	Bellatrix	252.4	10.2	66	Alphecca	77.2	1.79
27	Elnath	133.9	1.9	67	Mintaka	692.5	85.
28	Miaplacidus	113.2	0.43	68	Sadr	1830	270
29	Alnilam	1980	540	69	Eltanin	154.3	0.7
30	Regor	1120	110	70	Schedar	231.5	8.2
31	Alnair	101.0	0.66	71	Naos	1080	40
32	Alnitak	736.	106.	72	Almach	393.0	49.
33	Alioth	82.55	0.42	73	Caph	54.7	0.35
34	Dubhe	122.9	2.2	74	Izar	235.9	8.4
35	Mirfak	506.	13.	75	alpha Lupi	464.6	11.
36	Wezen	1610	300	76	epsilon Centauri	427.5	27.
37	Sargas	300.	41.	77	Dschubba	491.2	66.
38	Kaus Australis	143.3	1.5	78	Larawag	63.7	0.27
39	Avior	605.	47.	79	eta Centauri	305.7	6.0
40	Alkaid	103.9	0.79	80	Merak	84.5	2.5

Notable Star-Pair Angles

Notable star pairs (from the set of the 80 brightest stars listed above) that are close to a multiple of 5° separation. The angles are in degrees.

		Θ	$\Delta\theta$	defect (%)
Schedar	Caph	5	-0.085	1.7
Betelgeuse	Alnitak	10	0.017	0.17
Capella	Castor	30	-0.023	0.077
Procyon	Mirzam	30	-0.094	0.31
Elnath	Alnilam	30	-0.096	0.32
Alpheratz	Caph	30	0.060	0.20
Aldebaran	Pollux	45	0.013	0.029
Betelgeuse	Algol	50	-0.033	0.066
Alnitak	Naos	50	-0.049	0.098
Pollux	Alioth	60	0.065	0.11
Gacrux	Alphard	60	-0.001	0.002
Regulus	Bellatrix	70	-0.030	0.043
Sirius	Mirfak	80	-0.094	0.12
alpha_Centauri	Regulus	90	0.057	0.063
Vega	Denebola	90	-0.065	0.072
Fomalhaut	Caph	90	0.006	0.007
Deneb	Alnilam	120	0.059	0.049
Menkent	Mintaka	120	0.000	0.000
Sirius	Alphecca	135	-0.089	0.066
Aldebaran	Antares	170	-0.021	0.012

Exeunt

Lois's Theme

Can you read my mind?
Do you know what it is that you do to me?
I don't know who you are.
Just a friend from another star.

Here I am, like a kid out of school
holding hands with a god. I'm a fool.
Will you look at me, quivering. Like a little girl, shivering.
You can see right through me.

Can you read my mind?
Can you picture the things I'm thinking of?
Wondering why you are all the wonderful things you are.

You can fly! You belong in the sky.
You and I could belong to each other.
If you need a friend, I'm the one to fly to.

If you need to be loved.
Here I am, read my mind.

From the movie
"Superman" (1978)

ORION and TAO (and Obed) General Information (links)

May be found at the following URLs:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tamke-Allan_Observatory

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Where is TAO?

334 Caney Creek Rd, Rockwood, TN 37854

N 35° 49' 57", W 84° 37' 04"; Alt. 324 m

Where is Obed?

Lilly Bluff Overlook

N 36° 06' 09", W 84° 43' 17"; Alt. 402 m

Nemo Bridge (on the bridge, E bank of Emory River)

N 36° 04' 07", W 84° 39' 43"; Alt. 268 m

Trapezium back issues online, at CERN's zenodo database:

A full CERN zenodo doi url is for example <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219253>;
a short form, *e.g.* zenodo.org/records/8219253, may also be used.

Vol. 49, Issue 4; Fri 15 Apr 2023:	zenodo.org/records/8219253
Vol. 49, Issue 5; Fri 12 May 2023:	8216818
Vol. 49, Issue 6; Fri 16 Jun 2023:	8030659
Vol. 49, Issue 7; Fri 14 Jul 2023:	8140396
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Vol. 50, Issue 07, Fri 12 Jul 2024:	12735071
Vol. 50, Issue 08, Fri 16 Aug 2024:	13333599
Vol. 50, Issue 09, Fri 13 Sep 2024:	13742825
Vol. 50, Issue 10, Fri 11 Oct 2024:	13921735
Vol. 50, Issue 11, Fri 15 Nov 2024:	14171218
Vol. 50, Issue 12, Fri 13 Dec 2024:	14394899
Vol. 51, Issue 01, Fri 10 Jan 2025:	14630165
Vol. 51, Issue 02, Fri 14 Feb 2025:	14873015
Vol. 51, Issue 03, Fri 14 Mar 2025:	15015954
Vol. 51, Issue 04, Fri 11 Apr 2025:	15200349
Vol. 51, Issue 05, Fri 16 May 2025:	15443035
Vol. 51, Issue 06, Fri 13 Jun 2025:	15660329
Vol. 51, Issue 07, Fri 11 Jul 2025:	15865574

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Vol. 51, Issue 8; Fri 15 Aug 2025: zenodo.org/records/16884202

A generic link that lists Trapezium pdf issues (and other ORION documents) starting with the most recent, which does not require a specific zenodo document number, follows:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/rigel/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Fin du journal

“Black Hole Kitty”

So dense that light could not escape from her. -Ed.